

2-D DIAMOND/QUADRANT FIR DIGITAL FILTER BANKS WITH SHARP RESPONSES

Min-Chi Kao and Sau-Gee Chen

Department of Electronics Engineering and Institute of Electronics
National Chiao Tung University
Hsinchu, Taiwan, ROC
Tel: +886-3-573 1625; fax: +886-3-5724361
e-mail: sgchen@cc.nctu.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel design scheme, involving response sharpening process, for generating two-dimensional diamond/quadrant perfect-reconstruction (PR) linear-phase FIR filter banks with considerably reduced arithmetic operations, narrow transition bandwidth and good frequency selectivity. The scheme uses short 2-D Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) subfilters, preferably multiplier-free ones, as basic building elements. Starting from a diamond/quadrant PR FIR filter bank based on the subfilters, the proposed scheme algebraically composes the building elements such that it refines the 2-D filter bank into a new 2-D filter bank with better frequency responses. The scheme can be successively applied till a satisfactory diamond/quadrant filter bank is obtained. The proposed scheme results in a tree-like multi-stage cascaded structure. It is composed of shared building elements with trivial coefficients and short wordlength lengths, which is suitable for finite-precision realization. The structure is highly modular, repetitive in all stages, and thus very suitable for VLSI implementation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Most of the commonly used 2-D filter banks are based on separable tree-structured subband decomposition. This type of 2-D filter banks applies row and column filtering operations to 1-D QMF analysis filters in sequence. The separable structure has less complexity than that of a nonseparable one. Unfortunately, separable 2-D filter banks work satisfactorily only for applications of frequency separation. The properties of separable configuration are not equivalent to the aspect of different orientation sensitivities in the human visual filtering. In contrast, filter banks using nonseparable 2-D filters with diamond-shaped passband fit this feature more closely and could increase the system performance. Quadrant filter banks are also needed in some subband decomposition applications. Many design techniques had been proposed [1-8].

Another issue in FIR filter bank design and realization is the computational complexity. Since transition bandwidth is inversely proportional to filter length, the complexity of arithmetic operations is large for filters with sharp and good responses. For such problem Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) filters feature an efficient way of reducing significantly the computational complexity. Furthermore, the design of a low-complexity two-channel filter bank will be easier when choosing one of the analysis filters to be Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$), for examples, the diamond filter banks and quadrant filter banks in [6,7]. As such, the design problem reduces to the design of a Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) filter. The Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) approach [6,7] gave PR pairs of diamond/quadrant analysis filters, where the lowpass filter is Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$).

The mentioned design techniques involve optimization of the transformed 1-D half-band filter. One of their problems is that a sharp half-band filter is needed for a high-performance 2-D two-channel PR filter bank. Such design result suffers from the same problems as that of the traditional designs. However, the issue was not addressed in the mentioned papers.

Instead, it is preferable to use a short Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) subfilter as building element and simply cascade several of these building elements together. Here, such an approach is used to generate 2-D two-channel PR FIR filter banks with considerably reduced arithmetic operations, in which the Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) filter has a narrow transition bandwidth and good frequency selectivity.

In this paper we devise a new iterative design scheme. The scheme uses relatively short 2-D Nyquist($\mathbf{M}$) subfilters with trivial coefficients, preferably multiplier-free ones, as basic building elements. The subfilter with less computational effort is very easy to obtain. Based on the simple subfilters, 2-D high-performance two-channel PR FIR filter banks can be algebraically synthesized by merely cascading several of them. Filters designed with cascaded multi-stage approaches are easy to implement.

2 2-D FILTER BANKS BASED ON SHORT DIAMOND & QUADRANT-SHAPED SUBFILTERS

In this section, a new iterative design scheme is presented for the synthesis of 2-D diamond/quadrant PR linear-phase FIR filter banks. The basic concept of the scheme is that it alternately pulls up the passband gain and drags down the stopband gain of the Nyquist(**M**) filter to be refined. As such, an iterated Nyquist(**M**) filter with better performance is obtained. The refinement is achieved by algebraically composing some short Nyquist(**M**) subfilters..

2.1 Diamond FIR PR Filter Banks

Consider the design of diamond FIR PR filter banks with sharp responses. In this case, the lowpass synthesis filter is a modulated version of the highpass analysis filter, $G_0(\mathbf{z}) = -z_0 H_1(-\mathbf{z})$, and the highpass synthesis filter is a modulated version of the lowpass analysis filter, $G_1(\mathbf{z}) = z_0 H_0(-\mathbf{z})$. All the two analysis and two synthesis filters have the diamond-shaped passband. The PR condition for diamond filter banks is that $-z_0 H_0(\mathbf{z}) H_1(-\mathbf{z})$ is Nyquist(**M**).

We start with one short Nyquist(**M**) subfilter with diamond-shaped passband of the following form

$$\hat{H}(z_0, z_1) = \frac{1}{2} [1 + z_0^{-1} A(z_0 z_1^{-1}) A(z_0 z_1)], \quad (1)$$

where $A(z)$ is the polyphase component of some short 1-D half-band filter. Given a PR pair of 2-D diamond linear-phase FIR analysis filters $[H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), H_1^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})]$ generated in the k -th iteration and related by

$$H_1^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) = z_0^{-1} + z_0^{-1} [1 - 2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})] H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), \quad (2)$$

we would like to synthesize the $(k+1)$ -th pair $[H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}), H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})]$ with sharper diamond response. Provided that $[H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), H_1^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})]$ is entirely composed of identical Nyquist(**M**) subfilters $\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})$. We shall consider two types of synthesis in an iterative manner as follows.

(Type I). Refined by $\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})$: Define

$$H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) + [2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z}) - 1] H_0^{(k)}(-\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), \quad (3)$$

$$H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = z_0^{-1} + z_0^{-1} [1 - 2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})] H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}). \quad (4)$$

It follows that the response of the filter $H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ is linear-phase and Nyquist(**M**). PR is certainly preserved. Substituting $H_0^{(k)}(-\mathbf{z}) = 1 - H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$, gives

$$H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) + 2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) - 2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}). \quad (5)$$

As can be seen, both $H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ and $H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ are also entirely composed of identical Nyquist(**M**) subfilters $\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})$. The design process can be extended to arbitrary number of stages.

(Type II). Refined by $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$: One can improve the frequency selectivity of $H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ with the use of $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$ instead. Define

$$H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) [3 - 2H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})], \quad (6)$$

$$H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = z_0^{-1} + z_0^{-1} [1 - 2H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})] H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) [3 - 2H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})]. \quad (7)$$

As can be seen, both $H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ and $H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ are concatenations of the filters $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$.

2.2 Quadrant FIR PR Filter Banks

Next, consider the design of quadrant FIR PR filter banks with sharp responses. For quadrant filter banks, the lowpass synthesis filter is a modulated version of the highpass analysis filter, $G_0(z_0, z_1) = -z_0 H_1(-z_0, z_1)$, and the highpass synthesis filter is a modulated version of the lowpass analysis filter, $G_1(z_0, z_1) = z_0 H_0(-z_0, z_1)$. $H_0(\mathbf{z})$ and $G_0(\mathbf{z})$ have passband in quadrant I and III, while $H_1(\mathbf{z})$ and $G_1(\mathbf{z})$ have passband in quadrant II and IV. The PR condition for quadrant filter banks is that $-z_0 H_0(\mathbf{z}) H_1(-\mathbf{z})$ is Nyquist(**M**).

We start with one short Nyquist(**M**) subfilter with quadrant-shaped passband of the form

$$\hat{H}(z_0, z_1) = \frac{1}{2} [1 - z_0^{-1} z_1^{-1} A(-z_0^2) A(-z_1^2)]. \quad (8)$$

Given a PR pair of quadrant linear-phase FIR analysis filters $[H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), H_1^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})]$ related by

$$H_1^{(k)}(z_0, z_1) = z_0^{-1} + z_0^{-1} [1 - 2\hat{H}(z_0, z_1)] H_0^{(k)}(z_0, z_1), \quad (9)$$

Similarly, two types of synthesis are as follows.

(Type I). Refined by $\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})$: Define

$$H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) + [2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z}) - 1] H_0^{(k)}(-z_0, z_1) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), \quad (10)$$

$$H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = z_0^{-1} + z_0^{-1} [1 - 2\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})] H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}). \quad (11)$$

PR is also certainly preserved. As can be seen, both $H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ and $H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z})$ are also entirely composed of identical Nyquist(**M**) subfilters $\hat{H}(\mathbf{z})$.

(Type II). Refined by $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$: Define

$$H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) + [2H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}) - 1] H_0^{(k)}(-z_0, z_1) H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z}), \quad (12)$$

$$H_1^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}) = z_0^{-1} + z_0^{-1} [1 - 2H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})] H_0^{(k+1)}(\mathbf{z}). \quad (13)$$

3 DESIGN EXAMPLES

Design Example 1. First, consider the diamond case. Let's choose the fairly poor Nyquist(**M**) filter with diamond passband,

$$\hat{H}(z_0, z_1) = [(z_0^3 + z_0^{-3} + z_1^3 + z_1^{-3}) + 25(z_1 + z_1^{-1} + z_0 + z_0^{-1}) + 64 - 5(z_0^2 + z_0^{-2})(z_1 + z_1^{-1}) - 5(z_0 + z_0^{-1})(z_1^2 + z_1^{-2})] / 128,$$

as a subfilter. This 2-D filter can also be obtained by using the polyphase mapping on the 1-D zero-phase half-band filter

$$\hat{H}_{hb}(z) = (-2z^3 + 10z + 16 + 10z^{-1} - 2z^{-3})/32.$$

The half-band filter is multiplierless but has a fairly poorer frequency response than that of the Lagrange half-band filter $H_{hb}(z) = (-z^3 + 9z + 16 + 9z^{-1} - z^{-3})/32$. For better presentation of the evolution process of increasingly sharpening transition bands, Fig. 1 shows the diamond-shaped passband (depicted bright) and stopband (depicted dark) of the simulated 2-D frequency responses $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$. The change of transition bandwidth is perceptible. Fig. 2 shows the corresponding diamond-shaped contours. Regarding the evolution of the stopband attenuation, Fig. 3 shows the corresponding 1-D cross-sections of $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$ along the direction of $f_0 = f_1$. As shown, the response of $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$ is getting sharper with increasing k , that is, the band edges are approaching $|f_0| + |f_1| = \pi$ while the transition bandwidth is getting narrower, and the stopband attenuation is getting larger.

In this example, the resulting design is also completely multiplierless and is not subjected to finite wordlength effects.

Design Example 2. Choose the simple Nyquist(**M**) filter with quadrant passband,

$$\hat{H}(z_0, z_1) = \frac{1}{8}(-z_0 z_1 - z_0^{-1} z_1^{-1} + 4 + z_0^{-1} z_1 + z_0 z_1^{-1}),$$

as a subfilter. The simulation results for quadrant case are given in Fig. 4.

4 CONCLUSION

A novel design scheme was presented for sharpening the lowpass and highpass responses of a 2-D diamond/quadrant PR FIR filter bank. It is achieved by means of a recursive algebraic composition transformation. The transformation evolves a Nyquist(**M**) subfilter with diamond/quadrant passband to a composite Nyquist(**M**) filter having a very good frequency selectivity. Moreover, the repetitive use of the composition transformation results in tree-like cascaded Nyquist(**M**) subfilter

structures. The proposed structure also realizes a sequence of intermediate Nyquist(**M**) filter pairs of shorter sizes simultaneously. The proposed scheme is efficient and simple, because it is free of filter optimization required in many existing design methods. The proposed scheme is attractive for VLSI implementations in high speed, high complexity single-rate and multi-rate applications.

References

- [1] P. P. Vaidyanathan, *Multirate Systems and Filter Banks*. NJ: Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [2] J. S. Lim, *Two-dimensional signal and image processing*. NJ: Prentice Hall, 1990.
- [3] D. E. Dudgeon and R. M. Mersereau, *Multidimensional Digital Signal Processing* NJ: Prentice Hall, 1984.
- [4] R. Ansari and C. Guillemot, "Exact reconstruction filter banks using diamond FIR filters," Proc. Int. Conf. on New Trends in Comm. Control, and Signal Proc., Turkey, July 1990.
- [5] C. W. Kim and R. Ansari, "Subband decomposition procedure for quincunx sampling grids," Proc. SPIE Visual Communications and Image Processing, Boston, Nov. 1991.
- [6] S. Phoong, C. W. Kim, P. P. Vaidyanathan, and R. Ansari, "A new class of two-channel biorthogonal filter banks and wavelet bases," *IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing* vol. SP-43, no. 3, pp. 649-665, March 1995.
- [7] Y. P. Lin and P. P. Vaidyanathan, "Theory and design of two-dimensional filter banks: a review," *Multidimensional Systems and Signal Processing* vol. 7, pp. 263-330, 1996.
- [8] D. B. H. Tay, and N. G. Kingsbury, "Flexible design of multidimensional perfect reconstruction FIR 2-band filters using transformations of variables," *IEEE Trans. Image Processing* vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 466-480, Oct. 1993.

(a). $k=0$

(b). $k=1$

(c). $k=2$

Figure 1. The diamond-shaped passband (depicted bright) and stopband (depicted dark) of the 2-D frequency responses $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$.

(a). $k=0$

(b). $k=1$

(c). $k=2$

Figure 2. The corresponding diamond contours.

(a). $k=0$

(b). $k=1$

(c). $k=2$

Figure 3. The evolution of the corresponding 1-D cross-sections of 2-D frequency responses $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$ along the direction of $f_0 = f_1$.

(a). $k=0$

(b). $k=1$

(c). $k=2$

Figure 2. The quadrant-shaped passband (depicted bright) and stopband (depicted dark) of the 2-D frequency responses $H_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$.